

Refine linking criteria for portals to include periodic updates for key portals without long-term curation

{source:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1uuFyfMFFLaLOxjFstWjn6M_aNoA_L4HUzh0tVq1GjPs/edit}

Background

A set of criteria for assessing links from the DDC to non-dataset online resources was agreed in September 2014 (see http://www.ipcc.ch/meetings/TGICA/20Web1/doc2.12_1.pdf and document TGICA25 2-2c sup01). Some provisional assessments made using these criteria raised questions about the suitability of the criteria in section 4, “Stability of Resource”. In particular, the KNMI Climate Explorer failed these criteria (discusses at March 2017 Webex -- see document TGICA25 2-2c sup02). The site’s own documentation describes it as “a non-operational web service”. The site is of high interest to the climate impacts user community, so a review of the criteria was proposed.

Review

The KNMI Climate Explorer (KCE) is a well managed resource for the climate impacts research community, but, like many resources provided for and by the research community, it lacks long term financial commitments and is dependent on the intellectual input of a very small number of people (one in the case of the KCE). The KCE is nevertheless of very high value to the DDC user community.

In order to avoid confusion between such high-value resources and those which have a guarantee of stability, a new category might be introduced: provisionally approved links, requiring annual review by TGICA. The current decision guidance (*The resource will be linked to if a cumulative score of 5 or greater is obtained in each of sections 1 to 4, and the response to A5.2 is “no”.*) would be amended as follows:

The IPCC DDC has implemented a procedure for evaluating non-dataset resources (e.g. portals) held at other sites and linking to those that satisfy a range of criteria on quality, relevance to the IPCC and usefulness to the users of the DDC. The process is similar to the criteria for [linking to datasets](#). A full specification of the process is given provided in the [linking criteria specification \(draft\)](#). The process starts with the completion of a [questionnaire \(spreadsheet\)](#). Links to resources which pass are posted throughout the site. This page gives a comprehensive list, together with the completed questionnaires and associated evaluation reports. In many cases the portals provided limited information about the stability of future services: unlike datasets, the portals could be withdrawn or significantly changed. In such cases the links are subject to annual reviews.

A revised linking criteria document is submitted as
TGICA25_2-2c_revised_nonDatasetLinkinkCriteria.doc

Publication of approved links

The following page is on the site, but not yet linked from the menu:

<http://www.ipcc-data.org/guidelines/pages/approvedNonDatasetLinks.html>

Proposal: a menu link will be added under the link to approve dataset links.